

Contribution of Women to Household Expenditure in Rural Communities of Ughelli North Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria

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Author's contribution

The sole author designed, analyzed and interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

This study looked at the contribution of women to household expenditure in rural communities of Ughelli North Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The study objectives were to: Find out the socio-economic characteristics of women, identify the different income generating activities they are engaged in, determine their income level, determine their areas of contribution to household expenditure and determine their annual average contribution to household expenditure. Three communities were randomly selected from the seven communities in the study area. These were Ughelli, Ogor, and Orogun. Forty households were randomly selected from each community. A total of 120 respondents were drawn and data was collected using a well-structured questionnaire and interview schedule. However, only 105 responses were suitable for data analysis and were used. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, means and percentages. The study result showed a mean age of 45 years, 45.7% had secondary education, 61% were married with an average family size of 7. Their main income source was farming (69.5%). About 43% earned average cash income of ₦ 25,000 per annum. The total average income of respondents was ₦8,692,000. All of them contributed to food, clothing, education and health care except house rent to which just 12.4% contributed. The highest area of contribution was to food to

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which their total average yearly contribution was ₦ 2,125,000 which is 31.6% of their total annual contribution to household expenditure. Their average contribution was ₦ 6,735,135 which is 77.5% of their total average income. The study showed that the women use most of their income on their family needs. Their contribution in relationship to the average household size is not adequate to meet family needs. There is therefore need to mainstream gender into agricultural and empowerment programmes to remove bottlenecks experienced by women in areas of income generation to enable them improve their income level.

Keywords: Contribution; household; expenditure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Women contribute to household expenditure through engaging in income-generating businesses. Female borrowers use their income to contribute to household expenditure rather than to buy goods for themselves [1]. The main objective of women for taking loan is to contribute to their household livelihood. Women play multiple roles as generators of family's income, whether on household farms, businesses or as wage labourers, such work is essential for family survival [2].

Women in rural communities also play an essential role in the four (4) pillars related to food security: Food availability, accessibility, utilization and stability [3]. Resourceful women in rural communities contribute in a multitude of ways through different livelihood to lift their families and communities out of poverty. They work as unpaid and paid workers on the farms, they are traders and service providers, as leaders, and as caretakers of children and the elders [4]. Women are found in nearly every sector of the economy where they derive income for the survival of their household. They are reported to engage in more multiple income-generating activities than men. [5] Phumzile Mlanb [6] said in her statement to mark 2015 Rural Women's "Women have unparalleled opportunity and commitment to end poverty and hunger, achieve food and nutrition security, and guarantee sustainable livelihood in rural communities.

Men spend more of their income on items for their own consumption, including alcohol, cigarettes, high status consumer goods and even female companionship. Women are more likely to spend their income on household needs especially for their children. These include food, health care, education, clothing and personal care product [7].

Studies in developing countries like Burkina Faso, Rwanda and Malawi by [1,8] showed that

women spend their income on goods for their household more than me. This is true in developed and developing countries alike [8]. In United Kingdom for example women are responsible for more than three quarter of household expenditure. Usually when women have control over a couple's saving account expenditure shifts towards the purchase of family durable goods such as washing machines kitchen appliances, foodstuff and apparel [9].

Women have been found to control their family's nutritional status through food preparation and processing of food product. They also provide quality and sufficient food for their families through daily use of the available resources [10]. Research in Africa, Asia and American has found that improvements in household food security and nutrition are associated with women's access to income and their role in household decisions on expenditure. Women tend to spend a significant higher proportion of their income than men on food for the family [11]. Nutrition improves as women income increases. Child nutrition is better in household run by women than household run by men. Income managed by women has a fivefold impact on food expenditures compared to when men are the source of income. Women tend to invest in food which results in better health for the family. There is overall health improvement in household where women earn more than half of family income [12].

The study of women in Udu Local Government Area in Delta State by reported that the major income generating activity of women in the area of study is farming and farm related income generating activities [13]. Udu is inhabited by Urhobos with similar socio economic activities as women in Ughelli Local Government Area. Research findings further revealed that African women perform about 90% of the task of processing food crops, provision of household water, fuel wood, 80% of the work of food storage and preservation, transportation from

farm to village, 90% work of harvesting and marketing. They are also involved in cash crop cultivation [14]. The amount of income generated does not always determine the contribution to household concerns. Income generated can be channeled to other personal concerns other than household expenditure. Studies on women in developing countries like Burkina Faso, Rwanda and Malawi [1,2] posited that women bear the burden of providing for the family. The non availability of aggregated data on the areas and extent of contribution of women to family household expenditure in Ughelli North Local Government Area under scored the relevance of this study. The objectives of the study were to:-

1. Determine the socio-economic characteristics of women.
2. Identify the different income generating activities they are engaged in.
3. Assess their income level.
4. Establish their areas of contribution to household expenditure.
5. Determine their annual average contribution to household expenditure

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out in Ughelli North Local Government Area of Delta State. It is in Delta Central Agricultural Zone. It is one of the largest Local Government Areas of the State with an area of 818 km² and a population of 321,028 people [15]. It is located in the tropical rainforest zone of Delta State in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Its headquarters is Ughelli.

Three communities were randomly selected from the seven clans of the study area. The clans include Ughelli, Ogor, and Orogun. Forty households headed by male were purposively selected from each clan making a total of one hundred and twenty households. Male headed households were used because the women are not likely to be the sole contributors to the family expenditure. For female headed households they are the sole contributors unless where they have grownup children who may help in income generation. One hundred and twenty (120) women were interviewed using structured questionnaire and interview schedule. Fifteen of the questionnaires were not retrieved, which left a total of 105 which was used for the analysis.

Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics; Frequency counts,

means and percentages were used for statistical analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socioeconomics Characteristics of the Respondent

The result in Table 1 on socioeconomic characteristics showed that a great number of the respondents fell between age 42 and 51 years (54.3%). The mean age was 45 years. They were all within the range of active members of working population. Respondents were young enough to engage in income-generating ventures to support their families. The result on educational level of respondents showed that (48%) had secondary education and only (8%) had tertiary education. Most respondents were married (61%) with an average family size of 7. Their main income source was farming (73%).

3.2 Respondents' Income Level

The result in Table 2 on respondents' annual income showed that the minimum income level per annum was ₦10,000-40,000 and the maximum was ₦210,000- 250,00. A good number of the respondents were low income earners with (42.9%) with an average income of ₦25,000 per annum which is about ₦2,000 (approximately \$9) monthly. This confirms the findings of [16] which reported that 70.8% of Nigerians live on less than \$1 (approximately ₦300) a day which was the average exchange rate when the study was conducted. This is however their cash income since their main contribution is through their farm income especially in the area of food. In most cases like in this study it was not captured.

3.3 Areas of Contribution to House Hold Expenditure

The area of women contribution is shown in Table 3. This indicated the areas that women contributed in the rural households in the study area. It can be seen that all the women (100%) contribute to all main areas of household expenditure except rent. It is pertinent to note that all the women contributed to food despite the fact that most of their farm proceeds are consumed by the family. The result agreed with the findings of [7] that established that women spend their income to purchase goods for their household especially food, clothes, education and healthcare.

Table 1. Socio economic characteristics of respondents

Variables	Frequencies	Percentages	Mean
Age			
32-36	14	13.3	
37-41	14	13.3	
42-46	36	34.3	
47-51	21	20.0	
52-56	15	14.3	
57-59	05	4.8	
Total	105	100	45
Educational level			
Non formal education	29	27.6	
Primary education	20	19.0	
Secondary education	48	45.7	
Tertiary education	08	7.7	
Total	105	100	
Marital status			
Single	10	9.5	
Married	64	61.0	
Widowed	13	12.4	
Divorced	18	17.1	
Total	105	100	
Household size			
4---5	25	23.8	
6---7	39	37.1	
8---9	32	30.5	
10—11	07	6.7	
12---13	02	1.9	
Total	105	100	07
Sources of income			
Farming only	28	26.6	
Farming and trading	45	42.9	
Trading only	21	20	
Employment only	07	07	
Employment and trading	04	04	
Total	105	100	

Table 2. Respondents income level

Annual income level (in ₦)	Frequency	Percentage %	Total average mean income (in ₦)
10,000-40,000	45	42.9	1,125,000
41,000-80,000	18	17.1	1,089,000
81,000-120,000	10	9.5	1,005,000
121,000-160,000	15	14.3	2,107,500
161,000-200,000	11	10.3	1,985,500
210,000-250,000	6	5.7	1,380,000
Total	105	100	8,692,000

Table 3. Areas of contribution to house hold expenditure

Areas	Frequency	Percentage
Food	105	100
Health care	105	100
Clothing	105	100
Education	105	100
House rent	13	12.4

Table 4. Amount contributed to different areas of household expenditure

Items	Contribution to each item										Mean total contribution	% of ATC
	1,000-10,000		11,000-20,000		21,000-30,000		31,000-40,000		41,000-50,000			
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Food	14	13.3	54	51.4	23	21.9	05	4.5	09	8.6	2,125,000	31.6
Education	30	28.6	34	32.4	25	23.8	10	9.5	01	.9	1,680,000	24.9
Health care	46	43.8	34	32.4	12	11.4	13	12.4	-	-	1,495,000	22.2
Clothing	35	33.3	49	46.7	21	20	-	-	-	-	1,435,000	21.3
House rent	06	5.7	07	6.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	135	0.00
Total											6,735,135	100

ATC – Average Total Contribution

3.4 Amount Contributed to Household Expenditure

The distribution of respondents by average amount contributed to different household expenditure is shown on Table 4. It can be seen that the highest average contribution of respondents is to food (₦ 2,125,000) which is 31.6% of the average total household expenditure (THE). This is from their cash income. It is pertinent to note that the contribution of rural women to food is largely through their farm income since the primary occupation of 73% of them is farming. As a result of this, their farm harvest is geared primarily towards satisfying the family food needs. It is only after that, that they sell the surplus to meet needs in other areas of house hold needs or buy those food items that they do not produce. The lowest average contribution is on rent (₦ 135) which is less than 1%. This may be because in most rural households, men provide shelter for their family. Also in most cases every man lives in his own house but where he has not been able to build his own house he lives in the family compound. Renting of accommodation is a new phenomenon in rural Nigeria especially in the study area where the settlement pattern is clustered.

Considering the very low income of women in the study area in relationship to the average household size of 7, it is most likely that men contribute substantially to family expenditure.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study revealed that women in the study area were engaged in different income generating activities where they earned various sums of money every year. All of them contributed to food health care, education and clothing. The income of women was found to be very relevant for

meeting their household expenditure. Most of their income was geared towards meeting their family needs. It is obvious that most of the income of the women in rural areas in Ughelli Local Government Area is spent on household needs. The more income they are able to generate the more money they are likely to spend to meet their family needs. Though women contribute a lot of their income to meet the family needs, but the income of women is too small to cater for the family needs in relation to family size. Therefore, it is most likely that the men contribute reasonably to the family income.

5. RECOMMENDATION

It is recommended that there should be a deliberate gender policy to mainstream gender into agriculture to remove bottle necks that limit the production level of women and increase their ability to generate more income. This is because it will improve the quality of lives of rural families.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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